

A digital strategy for managing geometric manufacturing deviations in modular carbon-reinforced concrete origami structures

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Abstract

The high-strength, lightweight, and corrosion-resistant properties of carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC), combined with the symmetry and compatibility of the origami-inspired waterbomb pattern, enable the creation of assemblies built from CRC waterbomb modules. This modular design concept facilitates the construction of structural members for efficient floor and wall systems with minimal material consumption. These systems can accommodate customizable shapes and sizes produced using reconfigurable foldable formwork in a precast technology and assembled at the construction site. However, geometric deviations from the formwork and fold-in-fresh casting reduce module compatibility, introduce stress concentrations on the contact surfaces, weaken the interlocking function, and ultimately lead to a premature localized failure of the whole structure. This work describes a digital solution to this problem by compensating for the unavoidable deviations via a combinatorial optimization approach. The method quantifies the geometric deviations through 3D scans and identifies an optimal arrangement within the assembly that minimizes those deviations.

Keywords: carbon-reinforced concrete, waterbomb origami pattern, folded thin-walled structures, modular structural systems, modeling of thin-walled shell structures, homogenization.

1. Introduction

Carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC) opens up new design possibilities for lightweight, thin-walled, and environmentally friendly structural elements [1, 2]. An example of that are carbon-reinforced concrete waterbomb modules inspired by origami-based folding patterns, which combines the malleability of the concrete, flexibility of the carbon reinforcement and the geometrical versatility of the origami pattern [3, 4]. Combining carbon-reinforced concrete with the waterbomb origami pattern provides vast geometric freedom, allowing assembly of waterbomb modules to be precisely designed and tailored for structural performance requirements, ductility, and overall size and shape.

Waterbomb modules exhibit inherent geometric compatibility and symmetry, enabling their assembly into a topological interlocking system, where degrees of freedom of the assembled modules are constrained based only on their geometry [5, 6, 7]. The assembly procedure involves inserting one

waterbomb module into an adjacent module through a slit-based connection [8]. The manufactured waterbomb modules are casted in flat state and then folded by a pneumatic folding machine while the concrete is still fresh. The complexity of the folding kinematics inherently introduces geometric deviations, usually on the scale of millimeters, resulting from the intricate mechanics of the folding machine.

These geometric deviations hinder ideal facet-to-facet contact during assembly, often resulting in small geometric misfits at the interface. As a consequence, when the structure is loaded, localized bending deformations are induced in the facets to force contact and accommodate the assembly and compensate the misfits, which causes premature local failure of the of the assembly.

To address and manage the unavoidable geometric misfit, a closed-form algebraic solution for the assembly procedure is developed. The closed-form solution provides a systematic approach in which the reconstructed waterbomb geometry, derived from 3D scans, is assembled by means of assembly constraints the enforces a compatible perfect assembly between the modules. Enforcing a perfect assembly enables the quantification of the misfit between assembled imperfect waterbomb modules. Furthermore, the combinatorial strategy systematically explores all possible arrangements of the manufactured waterbomb modules within the assembly. Thus, identifying the optimal combination and positioning of modules that minimizes geometric misfit reduces interface incompatibilities, enhances overall assembly compatibility, and ultimately lowers the risk of localized failure.

Furthermore, the initial steps toward the development of a simulation framework are introduced to the quantification of failure modes at the level of the modules, focusing on the structural performance analysis of individual waterbomb modules and briefly comparing them with experimental results. This framework will be further expanded to cover waterbomb assemblies and the impact of the geometrical imperfections to the assembly performance.

2. The waterbomb module geometry

The geometry of the studied folded modules is obtained based on the analytical solution of the symmetrically folded waterbomb pattern, and its length desing paramaters are proposed in [4]. Given the length design parameters a, b, c, e and the folding angle γ of the waterbomb pattern, the waterbomb module with the dimensions shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Representation of the waterbomb module and its dimensions.

3. Closed-form solution for assembling imperfect waterbomb modules

The waterbomb assembly is achieved by inserting the modules through their diagonal slits in the assembly direction, as illustrated in Fig. 2. This process results in a diagonally arranged pattern that forms the final assembled structure. For a compatible assembly, the facets between adjacent modules must come into contact. In the case of ideal geometry, this contact is achieved precisely. However, when assembling imperfect waterbomb modules, facet contact may not occur, which leads to a gap between the facets known as facet misfit. To quantify this misfit, a general assembly procedure is developed that satisfies the geometric assembly constraints and enforces facet contact.

The closed-form solution for the assembly procedure starts defining a fixed reference module, denoted \mathcal{W}_C , and positioning a second movable module to be assembled, \mathcal{W}_D . The main requirement for the assembly is that corresponding facets of both modules are brought into contact due to the insertion of module \mathcal{W}_D into module \mathcal{W}_C along the slits depth, as shown in Fig. 2.

Given two waterbomb modules positioned in a two-dimensional Euclidean space. Each module possesses two reference points at the centroid of each facet that establishes contact with the adjacent module defined in the local coordinate system with basis \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2 . For module \mathcal{W}_C , these are \mathbf{x}_{C1} and \mathbf{x}_{C2} , and for module \mathcal{W}_D , they are \mathbf{x}_{D1} and \mathbf{x}_{D2} . Each reference point is associated with a local normal vector of the facets: \mathbf{n}_{C1} and \mathbf{n}_{C2} for \mathcal{W}_C , and \mathbf{n}_{D1} and \mathbf{n}_{D2} for \mathcal{W}_D as shown in Fig. 2. Each module is embedded into the global coordinate system by the position of the origin of its local frame, denoted \mathbf{X}_C and \mathbf{X}_D , and by a rotation angle around the x -axis that defines the orientation of each module relative to the global frame α_C or α_D , respectively. The position of the centroid vectors \mathbf{x}_{C1} , \mathbf{x}_{C2} , \mathbf{x}_{D1} , \mathbf{x}_{D2} , and their corresponding local normal vectors are known input parameters. In addition, the global position \mathbf{X}_C and the rotation angle α_C of the fixed module \mathcal{W}_C are known. In contrast, the global position \mathbf{X}_D , and the rotation angle α_D , of the movable module \mathcal{W}_D are unknown. The goal is to determine the unknowns global position of the module \mathcal{W}_D , \mathbf{X}_{D1} , \mathbf{X}_{D2} , and α_D in a compatible assembled state. There are three assembly criteria that such that allows a derivation of a closed-form solution for the compatible assembly of waterbomb modules.

The first criterion ensures that the facets of the modules to be assembled are parallel. This means that the cross-product between the normal vectors of the facets \mathbf{n}_{C2} and \mathbf{n}_{D1} , when transformed into the global coordinate system using the respective rotation angles α_C and α_D must be zero. This means that the facets of \mathcal{W}_C and \mathcal{W}_D are parallel and establish contact. Based on that, the first criterion is expressed by:

$$|\mathbf{T}_{Cab}(\alpha_C) \mathbf{n}_{C2b} \mathbf{T}_{Dcd}(\alpha_D) \mathbf{n}_{D1d} \epsilon_{abd}| = 0 \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{T}_{Cab} and \mathbf{T}_{Dcd} are rotation matrices dependent on the rotation angles α_C and α_D , respectively, and ϵ_{abd} denotes the 2D Levi-Civita. Throughout this work, the indices a, b, c and d are used to denote tensor components following the Einstein summation convention.

$$\mathbf{T}_C(\alpha_C) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\alpha_C) & \sin(\alpha_C) \\ -\sin(\alpha_C) & \cos(\alpha_C) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{T}_D(\alpha_D) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\alpha_D) & \sin(\alpha_D) \\ -\sin(\alpha_D) & \cos(\alpha_D) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Assembly schema for imperfect waterbomb geometries via reference points \mathbf{x} and facet normals \mathbf{n} .

The second criterion requires that the projection of the vector \mathbf{v}_{D1a} in the global coordinate system onto the transformed normal vector \mathbf{n}_{D1c} is equal to the distance d between the two assembled modules. The distance d is defined as the length measured along the crease line from the peak point at the top of the mountain fold in the waterbomb module to the edge of the adjacent assembled module. Then, \mathbf{v}_{D1a} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{v}_{D1a} = \mathbf{X}_{Ca} + \mathbf{T}_{Cab}(\alpha_C) \mathbf{x}_{C2b} - (\mathbf{X}_{Da} + \mathbf{T}_{Dab}(\alpha_D) \mathbf{x}_{D1b}) \quad (3)$$

and the projection of \mathbf{v}_{D1a} onto \mathbf{n}_{D1b} for the given distance d is:

$$|\mathbf{v}_{D1a} \mathbf{T}_{Dab}(\alpha_D) \mathbf{n}_{D1b}| = d \quad (4)$$

where d is the distance between the the highest point of the mountain crease of \mathcal{W}_C to the edge of \mathcal{W}_D in assembly direction and vice-versa, as shown in Fig. 2.

Analogous to the second, the third criterion considers the projection with respect to module C . Then, \mathbf{v}_{C1a} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{v}_{C1a} = \mathbf{X}_{Da} + \mathbf{T}_{Dab}(\alpha_D) \mathbf{x}_{D2b} - (\mathbf{X}_{Ca} + \mathbf{T}_{Cab}(\alpha_C) \mathbf{x}_{C1b}) \quad (5)$$

The projected length of \mathbf{v}_{C1a} onto the transformed normal \mathbf{n}_{C1b} must also equal to the distance d :

$$|\mathbf{v}_{C1a} \mathbf{T}_{Cab}(\alpha_C) \mathbf{n}_{C1b}| = d \quad (6)$$

By fulfilling all three assembly conditions, we ensure that the facets establish contact when \mathcal{W}_C and \mathcal{W}_D are assembled.

To quantify the geometric deviation between the fixed module \mathcal{W}_C and the inserted module \mathcal{W}_D , we define a scalar misfit measure ϵ that captures the orthogonal distance between the contacting facets of the respective modules. This misfit is computed as the projection of the positional difference between the facet centroids onto the normal direction of the reference facet on \mathcal{W}_C .

Let $\bar{\mathbf{X}}_C \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\bar{\mathbf{X}}_D \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the global coordinates of the centroids of the corresponding facet on \mathcal{W}_C and the opposing facet on \mathcal{W}_D , respectively. The local unit normal vector to the facet of \mathcal{W}_C is denoted by \mathbf{n}_C , and $\mathbf{T}_C \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the rotation matrix that transforms local facet normals of \mathcal{W}_C to the global coordinate frame. The scalar misfit is then given by:

$$\epsilon_{C,D} = (\bar{\mathbf{X}}_{Da} - \bar{\mathbf{X}}_{Ca}) \mathbf{T}_{Cab} \mathbf{n}_{Cb} \quad (11)$$

Since the assembly between two waterbomb modules consists of two contact interfaces between the \mathcal{W}_C and \mathcal{W}_D , two distinct misfit $\epsilon_{C,D}$ and $\epsilon_{D,C}$ are obtained as shown in Fig. 2.

6. Evaluating best module arrangement in an assembly and the misfit between facets

The waterbomb assembly procedure follows a diagonal pattern, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Here, the indices D and C are substituted by the numbering of the modules within the assembly from \mathcal{W}_0 to \mathcal{W}_8 . The assembly process begins with the assembly of the central diagonal, which includes the central module \mathcal{W}_0 . Subsequently, the side diagonals are assembled with reference to their respective central modules, \mathcal{W}_3 and \mathcal{W}_6 . The full assembly is completed when the side diagonals are inserted to the central diagonal.

The black arrows in Fig. 3 indicate the module pairs where the three assembly constraints are enforced, resulting in zero misfit at those interfaces. In contrast, the remaining modules belonging to the side diagonals are consequently assembled without direct constraint enforcement at their contact interfaces, and therefore inherit the geometrical misfits as depicted in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Assembly arrangement and misfit $\epsilon_{C,D}$ and $\epsilon_{D,C}$ between assembled modules.

In the present study, assemblies are composed of nine scanned waterbomb modules denoted as WB300 up to WB308 obtained by [10], arranged into five full modules and four half modules, as illustrated in Fig. 3. Although all scanned geometries represent full modules, those positioned at the boundaries of the assembly are interpreted as half modules. This approach enables consistent reuse of the full-module geometries without the need for additional scans of halved module geometry. The assembly arrangement are defined by the permutation space of nine distinct scanned modules selected without repetition. Let \mathcal{A}^9 denote the set of modules selected for assembly. The total number of possible ordered assemblies is $|\mathcal{A}^9| = 9! = 3\,628\,800$. Calculating the misfit for all $9!$ possible combinations is computationally

unfeasible. Therefore, the misfit of a random subset of 100 000 different assembly arrangement were calculated. Based on the indexing from \mathcal{W}_0 to \mathcal{W}_8 , the corresponding waterbomb scan identifiers that result in an optimal assembly with minimal facet misfit are WB303, WB304, WB302, WB305, WB308, WB306, WB307, WB309, and WB301.

7. Experimental and numerical investigation of the waterbomb modules

7.1 Loading and support conditions

The waterbomb module is loaded by a displacement-controlled hydraulic cylinder in z-direction. The load is transferred to the module along its central crease line in x-direction by a steel patch. An elastomeric membrane is placed between the steel patch and the module to ensure that the load is transferred equality to the folding crease lines given the geometrical imperfections. The support is provided by two steel surfaces that allow rotation around the x-axis, ensuring that the valley facets remain in full contact with the supports even under displacement.

Figure 4: Test setup of the waterbomb modules and positioning of the LVDTs.

7.2 Model discretization, constitutive laws and material properties

To conduct the numerical analysis of the waterbomb modules a FE discrete approach is chosen. In this approach, each roving of the reinforcement grid is discretized by truss elements that are activated only under tension, and their position in the thickness direction is taken into account. The concrete is modeled by quadratic 3D prismatic shell elements with 12 nodes. Aiming at the simplification of the simulation, the central web is not discretely modeled. As the web acts as a stiffener in the geometry, it is idealized as spring elements applied to the upper half of the crease line, as shown in Fig. 5a). The spring stiffness constant is calculated based on the load and the displacement captured by the LVDT J and K.

The concrete material law considers the classical orthotropic smeared crack formulation for fracture in tension and the three-parameter Menetrey-William failure surface for hardening/softening plasticity in

compression, a detailed description of these models are available in refer to [9]. The carbon reinforcement material law is linear elastic.

The mechanical properties of the concrete are the mean values for cylindrical and cubic compressive strength, Young's modulus, splitting tensile strength, and flexural tensile strength at an average age of 41 day, respectively, $f_{cm,cyl} = 68.2$ MPa, $f_{cm,cu} = 81.5$ MPa, $E_{cm} = 24\,805$ MPa, $f_{ctm,sp} = 68.2$ MPa = 2.9 MPa, $f_{ctm,pr} = 7.2$ MPa [10]. The carbon textile reinforcement consists of grid of rovings with a spacing $s_{rov,warp} = 12.7$ mm and $s_{rov,weft} = 16$ mm and cross-section area of $A_{rov,warp} = 1.8$ mm² $A_{rov,weft} = 0.67$ mm², $f_{rov} = 1150$ MPa and $E_{rov} = 123\,880$ MPa. A perfect bond is considered for the interaction between the concrete and the reinforcement. The modeling approach was implemented in the commercial software ATENA [11] and are reproducible with any commercial or in-house finite element code as long as the material laws, discretization, boundary conditions and material properties are complied.

7.3 Load-deflection curve and failure mode

The load-deflection response obtained with the 3D discrete model matches the test results well in the uncracked state and accurately captures the transition from uncracked to cracked state of the structure. However, the 3D discrete model overestimates the stiffness near the failure, as shown in Fig. 5. The discrepancy in the stiffness arises because the numerical model assumes a perfect bond of the reinforcement and idealizes the central web with a linear spring. In contrast, in the experimental tests, cracks arise in the vicinity of the central web, as depicted in Fig. 6, because of the failure of the reinforcement at the deepest valley (Point A) at approximately 25 kN characterizing the first failure mode, which reduces the contribution of the web to the stiffness of the module. Furthermore, cracks at the facets of the valley (Point B) are present since the beginning of the cracked stage at 10 kN. Finally, the load is redistributed after the failure of the deepest valley (Point A), and the second failure mode occurs at the lower right slit (Point C) with the failure of the reinforcement. Fig. 6 a) shows the max principal stresses at the reinforcement and the stress distribution along the valley facets with concentrating values at the deepest part of the valley and Fig 6 b) shows the min principal compressive strain showing that the mountain creases under compression.

Figure 5: Boundary conditions and force displacement curve from the LVDT A at the mid-span.

Figure 6: a) max. principal stress at the reinforcement. b) min. principal strain at the waterbomb module. c) crack pattern at the bottom surface. d) crack pattern at the top surface.

8. Homogenization as an efficient tool for the design of waterbomb modules

The modeling of individual waterbomb modules as described in the previous chapter is a time-consuming and computationally costly task. For this reason, a homogenization approach is being developed for a more systematic, more efficient, and faster modeling not only of the individual waterbomb modules but also of waterbomb assemblies. The primary objective of the homogenization method is to simplify the system of equations by substituting the complex structure with a homogeneous material representation. In our multiscale approach, we utilize two distinct scales for computation: the macroscopic scale, denoted as M , which describes the loading and boundary conditions, and the mesoscopic scale, represented by m , which defines the geometry and stiffness properties. At the macroscopic scale, we discretize the structural element using standard shell elements, while a representative volume element (RVE) is applied at the mesoscopic scale. We employ a structure-structure homogenization approach in which the RVE maintains the same discretization as that employed at the macroscopic scale. Solving the boundary value problem (BVP) of the mesoscale results in a material tangent matrix \mathbb{D} for the RVE, that can also be computed independently of the macroscale problem to evaluate the stiffness.

To connect the mesoscopic scale with the macroscopic scale, we apply the Hill-Mandel condition [12]. This condition establishes energetic equivalence between the two scales and is expressed as follows:

$$\langle \mathbf{P}^m : \delta \mathbf{F}^m \rangle - \mathbf{P}^M : \delta \mathbf{F}^M = 0 \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{P} is the first PIOLA-KIRCHHOFF stress tensor and \mathbf{F} the deformation gradient. By applying appropriate boundary conditions, that can reconstruct the macroscopic strains to the RVE, we satisfy the Hill-Mandel condition. In this case, stress boundary conditions are implemented on the upper and lower surfaces of the RVE, while displacement boundary conditions are employed along the lateral boundaries [13]. Additionally, antisymmetric link conditions for the out-of-plane displacements are introduced to constrain rigid body rotations. The schematic homogenization procedure is illustrated in Figure 7. For each integration point (GP) on the macroscopic element level, a RVE is assigned. Following the application of the macroscopic shell strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^M$ to the RVE, we solve the mesoscopic boundary value problem (BVP). This process yields the homogenized shell stress resultant $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and the shell material tangent operator \mathbb{D} . Both tensors are returned to the macroscopic scale, which assembles them in their weak form.

$$\delta \mathbf{V}_i (\mathbf{K}_i \Delta \mathbf{V}_i + \mathbf{F}_i) = \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^{MT} (\mathbb{D}_i \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^M + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i) \quad (13)$$

Here \mathbf{V} is the vector of the global degrees of freedom, \mathbf{K} the global stiffness matrix and \mathbf{F} the global residual vector. The variation of a field is denoted by δ and the linearisation of a field by Δ . For a detailed derivation refer to [14]. The material tangent operator \mathbb{D} contains the averaged stiffness properties of the geometry and is composed as follows:

$$\mathbb{D} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{D}_m & \mathbb{D}_{mb} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbb{D}_{mb}^T & \mathbb{D}_b & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbb{D}_s \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

\mathbb{D}_m denotes the membrane stiffness, \mathbb{D}_b the bending stiffness, \mathbb{D}_s the shear stiffness, and \mathbb{D}_{mb} refers to the coupling terms resulting from eccentricity between the mid-surface and the reference surface. For our RVE we chose a single waterbomb module. Given that the structure is a folded shell structure, we employ a structure-structure homogenization approach. As illustrated in Figure 7, the RVE consists of assembled Reissner-Mindlin shells, that represent part of the complex macrostructure. This approach was already implemented by Heller et al. [13], who analyzed sandwich plates with comb-like cores.

Figure 7: Illustration of the structure-structure homogenization procedure showing the discretization and connection between the macro- and mesoscale.

A key difference from conventional shell homogenization is that the RVE is not comprised of solid 3D elements. Instead, it is discretized using shell elements. When selecting the RVE, two criteria must be met. Firstly, the size of the RVE must be smaller than that of the macroscopic shell structure. Secondly,

its dimensions should be chosen to ensure it captures the smallest repetition of the inner core structure to minimize the computational effort.

Conclusion

In this work, we have derived a closed-form solution for the assembly procedure of carbon-reinforced concrete thin-walled waterbomb modules considering their geometrical manufacturing deviations. The closed-form solution enables a digital representation of the assembly procedure of the waterbomb modules based on 3D scanned data of the manufactured waterbomb modules. The closed-form solution enforces a compatible assembly of the waterbomb modules, where adjacent modules are positioned in such a way that their valley and mountain facets establish contact. This leads to the transfer of the geometrical misfit to adjacent modules, where the compatible assembly is not enforced. Based on this approach, the assembly procedure is carried out in a combinatorial manner, aiming to find the arrangement of waterbomb modules that minimizes the misfit between the modules considering their individual geometric deviations.

Furthermore, the experimental setup with load and support conditions is explained and serves as the basis for the modeling of the waterbomb modules by means of 3D discrete approach. This approach can reproduce the stiffness and the failure modes of the waterbomb module even though a perfect bond between the matrix and the reinforcement and an idealized web is considered. To make the numerical analysis of the waterbomb assemblies tractable, systematic, and efficient homogenization approach is under development, where the heterogeneous structure is replaced with an equivalent homogeneous continuum that reproduces its macroscopic mechanical response while retaining information about the underlying mesostructure.

This study demonstrates that folded, thin-walled modules made of carbon-textile-reinforced concrete can serve as high-performance structural components. It highlights that manufacturing imperfections can be controlled and accounted for in the design of waterbomb assemblies. The findings also underline the importance of fast, nonlinear numerical tools capable of assessing the broad design space enabled by waterbomb folding patterns. Ongoing work will extend the present models and integrate them into a robust computational framework for rapid evaluation and analysis of large-scale assemblies.

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